

VIRTUAL RESEARCH ENVIRONMENT GOES LIVE: BIG DATA SHARED ACROSS SCIENTIFIC ANALYSES

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ABSTRACT

The EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) Future Project is aimed at bringing together diverse analysis workflows from Astrophysics and High Energy Physics communities by providing a reliable AAI framework, federated storage services with the required exabyte-scale data management needs, and a large computing infrastructure on which to run analyses. The project aims at demonstrating how a common platform could support the goals of Dark Matter and Extreme Universe Science Projects in the respect of FAIR data policies.

Such a platform is being implemented as a Virtual Research Environment (VRE), an ecosystem with different complexity levels enhanced by a Web UI interface; it already provides functionalities for data injection, replication and processing through a containerized jupyter notebook extension of Rucio, a Data Management framework developed at CERN. The backend infrastructure of the VRE is the ESCAPE Data Lake, a Kubernetes (K8s) cluster for data management and orchestration including a main server, an authorization server and an UI interface.

As the reproducibility of scientific results is becoming more and more crucial for the advancement of science and for testing new theories, as well as being useful to spark scientific collaboration, the project's aim is to expand and adapt the current ecosystem's capabilities to enable scientists to not only interact with experimental data locally during a workflow run, but also to flexibly spawn complete re-analyses and interact with large data sets from anywhere. For this, the integration with the VRE of Reana [1], a re-analysis platform developed at CERN supporting various computing backends (Kubernetes, HTCondor, Slurm), is a key step of the project. The power of Reana relies on the fact that it takes advantage of declarative (.yaml files), instead of imperative, data analysis approach and achieves extended portability thanks to recent advances of container technology in the general IT industry. Before the start of the project, Reana takes input files from the user's local storage, while after the project a Rucio 'data fetcher' is implemented in the Reana logic, so to be able to utilise Rucio files on remote storages within a Reana workflow run.

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1 Introduction

Data is growing at an exponential rate. According to recent statistics [2], internet users generate about 2.5 quintillion bytes (1×10^{18} bytes) of data each day. In a similar way, data from CERN experiments are also challenging to manage. As an example, LHCb experiment starting in 2022, selects 10 gigabytes of the most interesting LHC collisions each second (after processing 4 terabytes of data per second in real-time) for physics analysis [3]. Other research institutions are starting to produce similar amounts of data to CERN, and therefore need the ability to efficiently track the generated data while meeting the FAIR (findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability) principles. That is why data management and orchestration software frameworks are considered valuable [4].

In the current data-rich age, understanding how to analyze and extract useful conclusions from big data is one of the primary drivers of success. Despite the colossal volume of data created every day, only a small portion is actually analyzed and used for data discovery, improvement, and intelligence.

Open data alone is not sufficient to foster reuse and reproducibility in particle physics. It is also essential to capture structured information about the research data analysis workflows and processes to ensure the usability and longevity of results. [5]

A common problem, as stated in the literature [6], is that half of the researchers cannot reproduce their own results. That means that it is important to find ways of preserving analysis knowledge, like data and code, capturing analysis assets in digital repositories to facilitate their future reuse. This is the reason why (re-)analysis platforms that apply statistical and logical techniques to describe, illustrate, condense and evaluate data are also considered precious. Thanks to these recent technological developments [7], solving the challenges of sharing, reproducing and reusing results from physics analyses seems more feasible than ever.

The need for proper data management and (re-)analysis leads to the development of all-in-one collaborative platforms where data and analyses are available among users. The Virtual Research Environment aims to be such a platform; it encompasses and serves the purposes of not only particle physics (LHC) experiments carried on at CERN, but also high energy astronomy (CTA), neutrino observations (KM3NET), low-frequency telescopes (SKA) and gravitational waves (LIGO) searches. The advanced data and analysis technologies that have been developed to serve LHC needs are progressively becoming appealing to all of the other above experiments, as they are generating larger and larger amounts of data and are looking for similar solutions to analyse them efficiently.

On the three following subsections, an outline for the VRE is given, which mainly uses two software solutions developed at CERN: Rucio, a data management and orchestration system, and Reana, a reproducible analysis platform.

1.1 Between ESCAPE and EOSC-Future: The VRE

ESCAPE [8], named after European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ES-FRI research infrastructures, brings together the astronomy, astroparticle, and particle physics communities. With this, ESCAPE puts together a cluster with ESFRI projects with aligned challenges of data-driven research, with demonstrated capabilities in addressing various stages of data workflow and concerned with fundamental research through complementary approaches.

EOSC-Future [9] tries to develop a platform to produce versatile solutions, with great potential for discovery, to support the implementation of EOSC thanks to open data management, cross-border and multi-disciplinary open environment, according to FAIR principles.

The VRE is a collaborative online platform where EOSC-Future members are able develop

their Science Projects. It hosts and implements the services provided by the ESCAPE Work Packages to provide an environment where all the digital content of a scientific result or subject can be easily findable, accessible, and reusable. The VRE is the first proof of concept (PoC) that will put under production all the ESCAPE services in the context of the EOSC project.

1.2 Rucio

Rucio [10] is an open-source project, developed by the ATLAS, for managing community data. It provides services and associated libraries for allowing scientific collaborations to manage large volumes of data spread across facilities at multiple institutions and organizations. It offers advanced features, is highly scalable, and is modular. Rucio was originally developed to meet the requirements of the high-energy physics experiment ATLAS but now is continuously extended to support the LHC experiments and other diverse scientific communities.

1.3 Reana

Reana [11] is a reproducible analysis platform allowing researchers to run containerised data analyses on remote compute clouds. The analysis is structured based on four questions: (i) where is the input data and parameters, (ii) what code is used to analyse the data, (iii) which computing environments are used to run the analysis code, and (iv) what are the computational steps taken to arrive at the results.

Thanks to the declarative programming approach and the support for multiple workflow engines (CWL, Snakemake, Yadage) and multiple compute backends, Reana also allows using hybrid computational workflow paradigm where parts of the analysis is run on one compute backend whilst the other parts of the analysis are seamlessly dispatched to other compute backend based on high-throughput or high-performance computing needs of the step at hand. The reproducibility of computations is assisted by means of using software containers (Docker, Singularity) that fully encapsulate the computational environment. Scientists can maintain and compare list of past runs, share results with colleagues over the web interface, and more.

2 Project Implementation

An important aspect of the VRE framework is that it is both integrated with Rucio, and therefore a data management infrastructure, but aims at running on a computing cluster by exploiting Reana as a middle-man between the cluster components and the analysis jobs, to more efficiently enable analysis reproduction. An essential ingredient for its success is implementing a connection between Reana and Rucio, in order to directly access Rucio files through Reana. The project aim was therefore to develop a 'data fetcher' to bring Rucio files to the Reana workspace and vice-versa.

2.1 Project Impact & Background

In order for researchers to share their scientific workflows it would be useful to have a simple file, re-runnable by everyone at a later time, describing every step of their analysis. Such a file can be composed with Reana through a `reana.yaml` file (declarative language) as displayed in Code 1. Before the start of the project, the analysis workflow had to start from input files found in the user's local directory.

In a hypothetical scenario, a user would like to use some Rucio files, in order to analyze them using Reana and then have the analysis outputs into Rucio. The available actions between the local computer, Rucio, and Reana are captured in Figure 1. Because of the absence of communication between Reana and Rucio the following steps should be followed in order to use Rucio files from a Reana analysis:

Figure 1: Available actions between the local computer, Rucio, and Reana

1. Manually download data from Rucio before starting analysis
2. Run analysis with local files (Uploads files to Reana workspace)
3. Manually upload data to Rucio after analysis is completed

Code 1 demonstrates the yaml file of a Reana analysis, taking as input the local files (`code/gendata.C` and `code/fitdata.C`) and giving as output the local file (`results/plot.png`).

The exabyte scale of the data should be taken into consideration when it comes to Dark Matter and Extreme Universe Science analyses. Downloading and uploading such huge amounts of data locally is something impossible both in terms of storage and bandwidth. Moreover, there should be a way to make the analysis re-runnable on any system, which might not host the input data locally. The above problem leads to the creation of a mechanism that will provide the ability for Rucio and Reana to interact with each other. In this way, researchers would be able to describe their whole analyses in just one yaml file. For the above to be fully implemented, the following items need to be addressed:

- Single user-specific configuration for Rucio authentication. This is achieved by running a sidecar container (explained in the next section) which is responsible for creating the appropriate files needed.
- Changes in the Reana internals in order to initialize and configure the sidecar container if needed.
- Support for Rucio commands on the Reana side. This is achieved by providing pre-configured environments with rucio-clients installed.
- Documentation for the changes


```

version: 0.6.0
inputs:
  files:
    - code/gendata.C
    - code/fitdata.C
  parameters:
    events: 20000
    data: results/data.root
    plot: results/plot.png
workflow:
  type: serial
  specification:
    steps:
      - name: gendata
        environment: 'reanahub/reana-env-root6:6.18.04'
        kubernetes_memory_limit: '256Mi'
        commands:
          - mkdir -p results && root -b -q 'code/gendata.C(${events},"${data}")'
      - name: fitdata
        environment: 'reanahub/reana-env-root6:6.18.04'
        kubernetes_memory_limit: '256Mi'
        commands:
          - root -b -q 'code/fitdata.C("${data}","${plot}")'
  outputs:
    files:
      - results/plot.png
  
```

Code 1: Example yaml file

2.2 Rucio Sidecar Container

The Virtual Organization Membership Service (VOMS) is at the core of the authorisation stack of the Worldwide LHC Computing Grid (WLCG). VOMS provides information about the relationship between researchers and their Virtual Organizations (VOs). The VOs manage users and grant them permissions according to their groups and roles. At CERN, all the various experimental collaborations such as ALICE, ATLAS, CMS and LHCb have their own VO. Being part of a VO can give you access to the globally distributed data analysis infrastructure of the collaboration. If a workflow needs special data access rights using permissions granted by your Virtual Organization, VOMS proxy authentication technique should be used.

The main inspiration for this section was the already implemented [Reana VOMS proxy sidecar container](#). From this image, a sidecar container [12] can be created. That container is initialized before the main job container runs and takes care of VOMS proxy initialization process by providing a VOMS proxy file based on previously-uploaded user secrets; hence the main research job container has full access to VOMS resources later during the runtime of the job, anytime it runs.

Rucio offers several authentication methods, like OIDC, VOMS, x509, GSS, SSH key exchange, username/password, etc. As VOMS authentication is already provided by Reana, the VOMS route is the simplest approach to combine Reana and Rucio.

In the background, when Reana orchestrates the execution of a job with the Rucio au-

thentication activated, it will automatically create a sidecar container that will perform the necessary Rucio configuration beforehand, using the secrets the user uploaded before starting the analysis. The VOMS and Rucio authentications require different kinds of secrets passed as ENV variables:

- VOMS proxy: the user needs to upload user key, user cert, VO pass, VO name, out of which the reana-auth-vomsproxy sidecar will produce a proxy file. That is all that is necessary for a job to access VOMS during runtime.
- Rucio: the user needs to upload their individual Rucio username. Using this and the VOMS proxy file the reana-auth-rucio sidecar will produce the Rucio configuration file (rucio.cfg). An example file can be found in Code 2.

```
[client]
rucio_host = https://escape-rucio.cern.ch
auth_host = https://escape-rucio-auth.cern.ch
ca_cert = /rucio_cache/CERN-bundle.pem
auth_type = x509_proxy
account = akouneli
client_x509_proxy = /vomsproxy_cache/x509up_proxy
request_retries = 3

[policy]
permission = escape
schema = escape
lfn2pfn_algorithm_default = hash
support = https://github.com/rucio/rucio/issues/
support_rucio = https://github.com/rucio/rucio/issues/
```

Code 2: Example rucio.cfg file

The command to add the Reana-secrets:

```
$ reana-client secrets-add --file userkey.pem \
    --file usercert.pem \
    --env VOMSPROXY_PASS=XXXXXX \
    --env VONAME=escape \
    --env RUCIO_USERNAME=rucio_username
```

The pod generated by every job which needs VOMS proxy and Rucio authentication is as shown in Figure 2

2.3 Reana components changes

Surrounding changes were made to Reana components, like (i) enriching OpenAPI specs and API client (reana-commons), and (ii) exposing rucio option (true/false) to workflow every engine. Setting `rucio:true` launches any necessary handshake with the remote Rucio instance that the user wants to connect to and creates rucio.cfg.

Most changes have been implemented on the reana-job-controller. There, new configuration variables were added in as show in Code 3.

Figure 2: The containers inside a job pod with support for VOMS proxy and Rucio authentication

```

RUCIO_CONTAINER_IMAGE = os.getenv(
    "RUCIO_CONTAINER_IMAGE", "reanahub/reana-auth-rucio:1.0.0"
)
"""Default docker image of RUCIO sidecar container."""

RUCIO_CONTAINER_NAME = "reana-auth-rucio"
"""Name of RUCIO sidecar container."""

RUCIO_CACHE_LOCATION = "/rucio_cache/"
"""Directory of Rucio cache.
This directory is shared between job & Rucio container."""

RUCIO_CFG_CACHE_FILENAME = "rucio.cfg"
"""Name of the RUCIO configuration cache file."""

RUCIO_CERN_BUNDLE_CACHE_FILENAME = "CERN-bundle.pem"
"""Name of the CERN Bundle cache file."""

```

Code 3: Part of the config.py file

On top of this, a function that initializes the sidecar container, mounts a volume visible from the job container and executes some basic commands is created. These commands are responsible for:

- exporting environment variables related to rucio account, rucio host, rucio auth host inside the sidecar contained environment.
- copying the CERN-bundle.pem file to a predefined path.
- running a Jinja2 command to create the rucio.cfg using the above environment variables at a predefined path.

Currently, Rucio requires VOMS authentication meaning that `voms_proxy:true` has also to be declared. Regarding the .cfg file, Rucio host and Rucio auth host are calculated by taking into consideration the VONAME environment variable.

Figure 3: Reana's code components that changes were applied to.

2.4 Rucio compatible analysis environments

The pre-configured environment options in order to run a workflow that requires Rucio commands are three:

1. Reuse sidecar container image as environment for the client staging jobs too (already done for Kerberos)
2. Use `reanahub/reana-env-rucioclient`, a basic image with support for Rucio commands.
3. Use `reanahub/reana-env-root6`, an image with encapsulated runtime execution environment for ROOT6 based data analyses. Prior to my contributions, this image didn't support Rucio. I switched CentOS7 (solves an existing [issue](#)) and installed the required libraries by Rucio (`rucio-clients`, `gfal2`).

Of course users can always use their own Rucio environments to run their workflows.

2.5 Documentation Enrichment

Every change on the Reana code should be followed by the appropriate documentation. A new page under docs.reana.io/advanced-usage/access-control/rucio/ was created describing in detail the Rucio integration.

3 Demo

Code 4 demonstrates a yaml file of a typical Reana workflow which uses Rucio files and uploads the results to Rucio. This example was also presented before but it was making use of local files only. Now, except for the two computational steps (gendata and fitdata), two more Rucio data-related steps have been added. The first one (fetchdata) is a stage-in step where Rucio files are getting fetched by running a `rucio get` command. The last one (uploaddata) is a stage-out step where local files are uploaded to Rucio. After exporting Reana's environment variables and adding Reana secrets, the workflow is ready to be created, uploaded and started, as shown in Figure 4. The Reana UI is an easy way to keep track of the process from the start (Figure 5) to the end (Figure 6). In this way, the file is runnable by anyone with a Reana and Rucio account and from any remote machine.

```
[root@agisvm-large secrets]# export REANA_SERVER_URL=https://localhost:30443
[root@agisvm-large secrets]# export REANA_ACCESS_TOKEN=

(reana) [root@agisvm-large secrets]# reana-client secrets-add --file userkey.pem --file usercert.pem --env VOMSPROXY_PASS= --env VONAME=escape --env RUCIO_USERNAME=akouneli --overwrite
==> SUCCESS: Secrets VOMSPROXY_PASS, VONAME, RUCIO_USERNAME, userkey.pem, usercert.pem were successfully uploaded.

(reana) [root@agisvm-large reana-demo-root6-roofit]# ./create_upload_start.sh
==> Verifying REANA specification file... /root/reana-demo-root6-roofit/reana.yaml
-> SUCCESS: Valid REANA specification file.
==> Verifying REANA specification parameters...
-> SUCCESS: REANA specification parameters appear valid.
==> Verifying workflow parameters and commands...
-> SUCCESS: Workflow parameters and commands appear valid.
==> Verifying dangerous workflow operations...
-> SUCCESS: Workflow operations appear valid.
==> Verifying compute backends in REANA specification file...
-> SUCCESS: Workflow compute backends appear to be valid.
myanalysis.106
==> Detected .gitignore file. Some files might get ignored.
==> SUCCESS: myanalysis is pending
```

Figure 4: Procedure of Reana workflow execution

4 Further implementations

Currently, the fetch and upload of Rucio files is being done by direct Rucio client calls. The stage-in and stage-out processes could be automatized even further. The `reana.yaml` could be enriched so that the input files section will support syntax like `rucio(my_instance,`


```

workflow:
  type: serial
  specification:
    steps:
      - name: fetchdata
        voms_proxy: true
        rucio: true
        environment: 'projectescape/rucio-client'
        commands:
          - rucio get agis_test:fitdata.C agis_test:gendata.C
      - name: gendata
        environment: 'reanahub/reana-env-root6:6.18.04'
        kubernetes_memory_limit: '256Mi'
        commands:
          - mkdir -p results && root -b -q 'agis_test/gendata.C(${events},"${data}")'
      - name: fitdata
        environment: 'reanahub/reana-env-root6:6.18.04'
        kubernetes_memory_limit: '256Mi'
        commands:
          - root -b -q 'agis_test/fitdata.C("${data}","${plot}")'
      - name: uploaddata
        voms_proxy: true
        rucio: true
        environment: 'projectescape/rucio-client'
        commands:
          - rucio upload --scope agis_test results/plot.png --rse EULAKE-1

```

Code 4: YAML file of demo workflow

my_scope, my_file) and when Reana will recognise these "external file definitions", it would internally do the stage-in from external sources such as Rucio all automatically. This is similar to [what Snakemake does](#), by supporting remote providers. Another implementation that would enrich the overall Rucio - Reana integration for ESCAPE users would be the full transition from authentication with X509 certificates to tokens, and have Reana accept the same token that is now used to authenticate to the ESCAPE Data Lake and to Rucio.

5 Code availability

Because of the very large scale of the project, GitHub is used as a version control system designed to handle everything with high speed and efficiency. The main issue can be found here: github.com/reanahub/reana-auth-rucio/issues/1. As it appears, nine (9) PRs close this issue. A separate Pull Request can be found here: github.com/reanahub/reana-env-rucioclient/pull/1

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Figure 5: Workflow running status

Figure 6: Workflow finished status

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References

- [1] Tibor Šimko et al. “Scalable declarative hep analysis workflows for containerised compute clouds”. In: *Frontiers in big Data* 4 (2021), p. 661501.
- [2] Arvind Murali. *Understanding Generation Data*. URL: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbestechcouncil/2021/08/02/understanding-generation-data> (visited on 08/24/2022).
- [3] Cristina Agrigoroae. *LHC experiments are stepping up their data processing game*. URL: <https://home.cern/news/news/computing/lhc-experiments-are-stepping-their-data-processing-game> (visited on 08/24/2022).
- [4] Oracle. *What Is Data Management?* URL: <https://www.oracle.com/database/what-is-data-management/> (visited on 09/06/2022).
- [5] Xiaoli Chen et al. “Open is not enough”. In: *Nature Physics* 15.2 (2019), pp. 113–119.
- [6] Monya Baker. “1,500 scientists lift the lid on reproducibility”. In: *Nature* 533.7604 (2016).
- [7] Sünje Dallmeier-Tiessen and Tibor Šimko. *Open science: A vision for collaborative, reproducible and reusable research*. URL: <https://cerncourier.com/a/open-science-a-vision-for-collaborative-reproducible-and-reusable-research/> (visited on 08/31/2022).
- [8] *ESCAPE (European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures)*. URL: <https://projectescape.eu/> (visited on 09/06/2022).
- [9] *EOSC Future*. URL: <https://eoscfuture.eu/> (visited on 09/06/2022).
- [10] Martin Barisits et al. “Rucio: Scientific Data Management”. In: *Computing and Software for Big Science* 3.1 (2019), p. 11. ISSN: 2510-2044. DOI: 10.1007/s41781-019-0026-3. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41781-019-0026-3>.
- [11] Tibor Šimko et al. “REANA: A system for reusable research data analyses”. In: *EPJ web of conferences*. Vol. 214. EDP Sciences. 2019, p. 06034.
- [12] Ed Seymour. *Kerberos Sidecar Container*. URL: <https://cloud.redhat.com/blog/kerberos-sidecar-container> (visited on 08/31/2022).

